

Undergraduate students' conceptual understanding of electromagnetic waves

Marco COSTIGLILO^{0009-0009-5187-3390, 1}, Matteo BOZZI^{0000-0002-8117-6379, 1},
Danilo CATENA^{0000-0003-2787-4368, 2}, Marisa MICHELINI^{0000-0003-4764-9774, 2},
Lorenzo SANTI^{0000-0002-2130-587X, 2}, Maurizio ZANI^{0000-0001-7960-3362, 1}

¹ Politecnico di Milano, Department of Physics, Milan, Italy

² University of Udine, Department of Mathematics, Physics and Computer Science, Udine, Italy

marco.costigliolo@polimi.it

Appendix A. Electromagnetic waves questions

Question 1

The figure shows an electromagnetic wave at time $t = 0$. The electric and magnetic fields oscillate sinusoidally. Both the electric and magnetic fields take the same values at all points in space that belong to a plane parallel to the y - z plane. Let T be the period of the wave. Which of the following options correctly represents the order of the intensities of the electric and magnetic fields at points A, B, and C at time $t = T$?

- a) $E_Q > E_P = E_R$ and $B_P = B_Q = B_R$
- b) $E_P = E_Q = E_R$ and $B_P = B_Q = B_R$
- c) $E_P > E_Q > E_R$ and $B_P = B_Q = B_R$
- d) $E_P > E_Q > E_R$ and $B_P > B_Q > B_R$
- e) None of the above options

Correct answer: b) $EP = EQ = ER$ and $BP = BQ = BR$.

Explanation: Given the planar symmetry of the wave, the electric and magnetic fields take the same values at all points lying in a plane parallel to the y-z plane. This is precisely the case for points P, Q, and R.

Question 2

Four students are discussing the types of motion a point electric charge must have with respect to an inertial reference frame S in order to generate an electromagnetic wave detectable in all inertial frames.

Student A says: "A point electric charge at rest in S can generate an electromagnetic wave."

Student B replies: "I disagree, because a stationary charge does not generate time-varying electric and magnetic fields. Therefore, the charge must move with uniform motion."

Student C replies: "I disagree, because even in that case the generated fields are constant. Therefore, we need a charge that moves with accelerated motion."

Student D replies: "I disagree, because even a uniformly moving charge can generate time-varying fields, but not in all inertial frames. For this reason, we need an accelerated charge." With whom do you agree?

- a) With Student A
- b) With Student B
- c) With Student C
- d) With Student D
- e) With none of the students

Correct answer: d) With Student D.

Explanation: A uniformly moving charge does generate time-varying fields (it is not equivalent to a DC current). However, the motion depends on the reference frame adopted, so only an accelerated charge ensures the electromagnetic field detected in all inertial frames is time-varying.

Question 3

Consider the following cases:

1. An electric field $E_1(t)$, varying sinusoidally in time, propagates in a simple dielectric medium D with frequency f_1 .
2. An electric field $E_2(t)$, also varying sinusoidally in time, propagates in the same dielectric medium D with frequency $f_2 > f_1$.
3. An electric field $E_3(t)$, varying sinusoidally in time, propagates in a vacuum with frequency $f_3 < f_1$.

All three fields originate from the same point O in space, propagate in the same direction, and are detected at point P.

Let t_i be the time interval required for field E_i to be detected at point P. Which of the following statements is correct?

- a) $t_1 = t_2 = t_3$
- b) $t_2 > t_1 > t_3$
- c) $t_2 = t_1 > t_3$
- d) $t_3 > t_1 > t_2$
- e) None of the above options

Correct answer: c) $t_2 = t_1 > t_3$.

Explanation: The propagation medium affects the wave velocity due to refraction. Therefore, the highest speed is observed in vacuum. In contrast, the oscillation frequency does not affect the propagation speed.

Question 4

An observer at rest in an inertial reference frame S, with a portable radio, receives a signal from a radio wave source. Consider the following cases:

1. The source is at rest in S.
2. The source is moving away from the observer with uniform motion relative to S.
3. The source is approaching the observer with uniformly accelerated motion relative to S.

Let v_i be the magnitude of the propagation speed of the radio signal as measured by the observer. Which of the following statements is correct?

- a) $v_1 = v_2 = v_3$
- b) $v_3 > v_2 > v_1$
- c) $v_1 > v_2 > v_3$
- d) Not enough information to answer
- e) None of the above options

Correct answer: a) $v_1 = v_2 = v_3$.

Explanation: The speed of electromagnetic waves is independent of the relative motion between observer and source.

Question 5

Consider the three adjacent figures. They represent the components along the direction of propagation of three electric fields that vary sinusoidally over time. These fields strike a surface lying in the y-z plane. The amplitudes of the three fields are respectively a , $3a$, and $2a$, while the wavelengths are 3λ , 2λ , and λ respectively.

Let I_i be the amount of energy striking surface A in 1 second. Which of the following statements is correct?

- a) $I_1 > I_2 > I_3$
- b) $I_3 > I_2 > I_1$
- c) $I_1 = I_2 = I_3$
- d) $I_2 > I_3 > I_1$
- e) None of the above options

Correct answer: d) $I_2 > I_3 > I_1$.

Explanation: Classical electromagnetic theory shows that wave intensity is proportional to the square of the field amplitude and is independent of wavelength.

Question 6

A graph shows the time evolution of an electromagnetic wave at a point P. A portable radio is used to detect this signal at point P.

In which direction should the radio antenna be oriented to achieve the best reception?

- a) In the direction of the y-axis
- b) In the direction of the z-axis
- c) In the direction perpendicular to the y-z plane
- d) The best direction changes over time
- e) None of the above options

Correct answer: b) In the direction of the z-axis.

Explanation: The best reception occurs when the antenna is aligned with the direction of the electric field, as it is this field that exerts a force to move charges in the receiver. The magnetic field's effect is always perpendicular to the direction in which charges can move and can be neglected here.